

Neglected Effects of Multicommutation in 2-Level SiC Inverters: Insights into Switching Behavior

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Abstract

This paper investigates multicommutation in modular SiC-based inverter systems, where simultaneous switching of multiple power modules increases the effective commutation loop inductance, causing higher voltage overshoot, stronger oscillations, and increased turn-off losses. Experiments were performed on simplified single-phase setups and complete two-phase submodules with parallel-connected SiC MOSFETs. Results show that increased commutation loop inductance is the primary mechanism driving these effects, and that simplified setups can emulate multicommutation. Full-module measurements indicate that careful phase placement and low-inductance layout substantially reduce susceptibility to multicommutation, maintaining robust switching performance. These findings provide practical guidance for designing modular SiC inverters to ensure reliable operation under high-speed, multi-phase switching conditions.

1 Introduction

As wind energy systems continue to increase in both power and complexity, modern inverter architectures are increasingly modular and scalable. These systems often consist of multiple parallel inverter phases on both the generator and the grid side, interconnected via a shared DC-link.

In such modular systems, inverters are typically operated independently, only connected via the shared DC-link. This allows a wide range of possible switching patterns, including scenarios where multiple SiC MOSFETs undergo commutation simultaneously or within a few nanoseconds, an event referred to as multicommutation.

While multicommutation has been studied in the context of IGBT-based inverter systems [1], [2], it has received little attention in SiC-based converters. Due to the significantly faster switching transitions of SiC MOSFETs, multicommutation events can occur more frequently and may lead to increased electrical stress.

Minimizing parasitic inductances in the commutation path is essential for reliable operation. Even small parasitic inductances can cause significant voltage overshoots, oscillations, and increased elec-

tromagnetic interference (EMI), which directly affect device stress and converter reliability.

Fig. 1: 3D CAD model of the investigated two-phase inverter submodule, illustrating the physical layout

Therefore, this paper investigates the influence of multicommutation in modular SiC inverter systems. The study is based on a modular back-to-back inverter consisting of three phases on the generator side and three phases on the grid side. Experimental investigations are first carried out on a simplified setup representing half of the final inverter submodule, comprising two 2.3 kV SiC MOSFETs and four DC-link capacitors. In a second step, measurements are performed on a complete inverter submodule shown in figure 1. Consisting of two phases and an increased DC-link capacitor config-

uration. This approach enables the investigation of multicommutation effects different levels of system complexity, ranging from simplified configurations to converter-level conditions, and allows an assessment of the resulting voltage stress under different swicthing scenarios.

2 Converter Architecture and Commutation Loop

2.1 System-Level Constraints

Low-inductance inverter designs must balance practical system requirements with the goal of minimizing parasitic inductance. Limited space, pre-defined mechanical dimensions, and integration constraints restrict layout flexibility. In addition, the required energy storage defines the number and size of the DC-link capacitors, while the internal stray inductance of the SiC power modules is fixed and cannot be influenced by the system designer. These constaraints directly affect the achievable commutation loop inductance and therefore influence multicommutation-induced voltage stress.

2.2 Design Trade-Offs

Minimizing stray inductance requires careful coordination between capacitor integration and busbar design. Many of the optimization factors are not independent and may contradict each other.

Capacitor Integration: Increasing the number of parallel capacitors raises the total capacitance and reduces the parasitic inductance. Four-terminal capacitors generally offer lower equivalent series inductance (ESL) than two-terminal ones [3], [4]. Each terminal requires a dedicated busbar connection, and the number, placement and diameter of these connection holes can adversely affect the overall busbar inductance [5],[6]. High-voltage insulation constrains also limit how small these openings can be. Symmetrical terminal placement can reduce the stray inductance [5].

Busbar geometry: Wider busbars reduce the current density and magnetic field concentration, thereby lowering the inductance. Increasing the width is often restricted by mechanical limitations and the available space. In contrast, longer or thicker busbars and increased layer spacing enlarge the magnetic loop area,thereby increasing inductance [5]. All geometric, thermal, and mechanical factors must be carefully balanced to achieve a compact and low-inductance inverter layout.

2.3 Low-Inductance Inverter Prototype

Based on the identified constraints and design trade-offs, a modular back-to-back inverter prototype was developed, serving as the basis for the investigations in this work. Each inverter module consists of two phases equipped with 2.3 kV SiC MOSFET half-bridge modules and an integrated DC-link capacitor bank.

3 Experimental Setup

Multicommutation refers to scenarios where power switches - connected to the same DC-link - commute simultaneously or within nanoseconds of each other. These overlapping switching events lead to shared commutation paths, significantly increasing the effective parasitic inductance seen by each device [2]. This results in increased voltage overshoots, electrical stress, and the potential for undesired ringing.

To investigate multicommutation effects in a controlled environment, three test cases are defined and used for both the half-module and the full-module investigations.

Case A (Single Commutation):

describes the operation of a single power module connected to the full DC-link capacitor configuration, representing standard switching under low-inductance conditions.

Case B (Synchronous Multicommutation):

refers to the simultaneous switching of multiple modules sharing the same DC-link capacitor bank. The switching modules are arranged in close proximity.

Case C (Emulated Multicommuattion):

To simulate similar stress conditions with a single module. Multicommutation is emulated by artificially increasing the parasitic inductance of the commutation path as proposed in [2] for testing synchronous Multikommutation. In the test set up, this was achieved by varying the number of the DC-link capacitors. This allowed systematic analysis of voltage transients and switching behavior under increased commutation inductance, effectively simulating the electrical effects of multicommutation in a controlled, single-phase environment. In the half-module and the full-module setup the amount of capacitors is reduced by 50% for Case C.

3.1 Half-Module Test-Setup

To investigate the electrical effects of multicommutation under controlled laboratory conditions, switch-

ing experiments were first conducted using a simplified half-module test setup. The configuration represents a single phase of the developed modular inverter and consists of two 2.3 kV SiC MOSFET half-bridge modules connected to a configurable DC-Link capacitor bank.

The half-module test setup used for these measurements is shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2: Half-module of a modular inverter prototype with minimized commutation loop inductance. Closely integrated capacitors and a compact mechanical structure

The switching experiments were carried out according to the defined Cases A-C. In Case A, a Single MOSFET module was operated with four DC-link capacitors, representing a minimized commutation loop.

For Case B, both MOSFET modules of the phase were switched simultaneously while sharing the same DC-link capacitor bank. In this configuration, the commutation currents of both modules flow through the same common DC-link path.

For Case C, the commutation loop inductance was intentionally increased by reducing the number of active DC-link capacitors to two.

The distance between the reduced capacitor configurations and the power modules was also varied in order to further influence the commutation loop inductance. However, only one representative configuration is presented in this work, as it exhibits a switching behavior comparable to the synchronous multicommutation case.

3.2 Full-Module Test-Setup

In addition to the simplified half-module setup, switching experiments were also performed on a complete submodule of the developed modular back-to-back converter. Each submodule con-

sists of two inverter phases connected to a shared DC-link capacitor bank comprising eight parallel-connected capacitors. Each phase is equipped with two 2.3 kV SiC MOSFET half-bridge modules. The submodule features a compact and symmetrical layout, as illustrated in figure 1. Power modules are arranged on opposite sides of the DC busbar, with the DC-link capacitor bank located in between. The investigations were carried out according to the defined Cases A–C, applied to one inverter side of the full-module configuration.

In addition, measurements were performed with simultaneous switching of both inverter phases, including parallel-connected modules, to investigate multicommutation under representative converter-level conditions.

3.3 DC-Link and Commutation Loop characterization (Under construction Grafiken fehlen)

Fig. 3: VNA-based measurement of commutation loop inductance for a single module with varying capacitor configurations

In addition to the switching measurement, the commutation loop inductance of the investigated setups was characterized using a vector analyzer (VNA)-based measurements. The analysis focuses on the influence of the different DC-link capacitor configurations on the effective commutation loop inductance.

Measurements were performed for both the half-module and full-module setups with varying numbers of DC-link capacitors. This allows a direct comparison of the commutation loop characteristics under different configurations.

Figure 3 shows the results for the half-module. For the emulation of multicommutation results the of Capacitor combination of Capacitor 1 and Capacitor 4 was used.

4 Experimental Results

4.1 Half-Module Turn-Off Behaviour

Fig. 4: Pairwise comparison of the investigated switching cases under identical operating conditions in the simplified half-module setup, highlighting the impact of multicommutation.

For the half-module the three cases A-C were investigated and are compared in figure 4. Each subplot presents a pairwise comparison of the three cases to highlight the influence of multicommutation and increased commutation loop inductance. Additionally, the VNA-based measurements shown in figure 3 confirm the increase in commutation loop inductance for configurations with reduced capacitor count.

Multicommutation vs. Single Commutation

Synchronous multicommutation (Case B) exhibits a higher voltage overshoot and more pronounced oscillations compared to single commutation (Case A).

This confirms that simultaneous multicommutation increases the effective commutation loop inductance and therefore the dynamic electrical stress of the power modules.

Multicommutation vs. Emulated Multicommutation

The emulated configuration (Case C) with increased commutation loop inductance shows comparable switching dynamics to the synchronous

multicommutation. The voltage overshoot and the oscillation are of similar magnitude.

This demonstrates that the dominant factor governing the stress increase is the effective commutation loop inductance, which can be adjusted in the single-module setup to replicate multicommutation effects for MOSFETs, as proposed by the concept of virtual inductance for IGBTs in [1], [2].

Single Commutation vs. Emulated Multicommutation

When comparing single commutation (Case A) with the increased inductance configuration (Case C), the increased inductance case results in a clearly higher voltage overshoot and stronger oscillations. This confirms that an increase in commutation loop inductance alone is sufficient to reproduce the main stress mechanisms observed under synchronous multicommutation for this kind of setup.

4.2 Full-Module 1 Phase

The full-module measurements exhibit similar trends for multicommutation and single commutation as observed in the half-module setup. figure 5 shows a pairwise comparison of Cases A–C.

Fig. 5: Pairwise comparison of the investigated switching cases under identical operating conditions, obtained from the complete inverter submodule.

Emulated Multicommutation vs. Single Commutation vs. Multicommutation

In contrast, the emulated configuration does not reproduce the same level of voltage overshoot and oscillation as synchronous multicommutation. Its switching behavior is closer to that of single commutation. This indicates that removing half of the DC-link capacitors alone is not sufficient to signif-

icantly modify the commutation loop inductance and fully replicate multicommutation conditions in the full-module setup. This observation is further supported by the VNA measurements.

Multicommutation vs. Single Commutation

Focusing on the real full-module setup, synchronous multicommutation results in a significantly higher voltage overshoot compared to single commutation, confirming that the increased dynamic stress observed in the half-module measurements also occurs in the full-module configuration.

Fig. 6: Comparison of single and multicommutation highlighting instantaneous switching power

The increased overvoltage and oscillations result in an average 4% increase in the peak instantaneous power and an average 8% increase in turn-off losses. This behavior is illustrated in figure 6, which compares single and multicommutation, including the corresponding instantaneous power dissipation.

Figure 7 shows the current and voltage waveforms at turn-off for different $R_{g,off}$ values. Independent of the switching speed, multicommutation leads to increased overvoltage and more pronounced oscillations. To achieve a comparable maximum overvoltage, a higher $R_{g,off}$ must be selected under multicommutation conditions than in the single-commutation case.

However, increasing $R_{g,off}$, as required to limit the overvoltage, results in higher turn-off losses (figure 8). Consequently, both commutation modes exhibit increased losses compared to operation at lower $R_{g,off}$, with multicommutation consistently showing higher losses. The turn-off energy under multicommutation is approximately 8% higher than in the single-commutation case.

Fig. 7: Measured results for single and multicommutation at different turn-off gate resistances $R_{g,off}$ 1.8 Ω , 2.7 Ω and 4 Ω .

Fig. 8: Comparison of turn-off losses for single and multicommutation as a function of turn-off gate resistance, highlighting the increased losses during multicommutation

4.3 Full-Module 2 Phases

In the final step, the full-module submodule of the back-to-back inverter, consisting of two phases with two parallel-connected power modules per phase, was tested. The switching behavior of this setup, where both phases are turned off simultaneously, was compared to the case of single-phase turn-off with two parallel-connected power modules, as illustrated in figure 9. The measurements show that the multicommutation event has little influence on the overvoltage or oscillation magnitude. Both single-phase switching and synchronous multi-phase commutation result in nearly identical waveforms in terms of overshoot and oscillatory behavior. Furthermore, the switching behavior of each phase

Fig. 9: Comparison of single and multicommutation in the full inverter module, illustrating the robust switching performance and low susceptibility to multicommutation.

is largely independent of the other phase, as also evidenced by the observation that turn-off with one module and four capacitors behaves very similarly to turn-off with one module and eight capacitors. These findings highlight that, in inverter systems, the overall system layout, including phase placement and parasitic inductances, can significantly affect switching behavior and may mitigate the effects of multicommutation, and thus the resulting electrical stress on the power modules. In the present design, the chosen arrangement and layout effectively reduce the susceptibility to multicommutation, demonstrating the robustness of the developed inverter submodule.

5 Discussion

The experimental results demonstrate that multicommutation in SiC-based inverter systems leads to increased voltage overshoot, stronger oscillations, and higher switching losses compared to single commutation. These effects are primarily caused by the increase in effective commutation loop inductance due to shared current paths during simultaneous switching events.

Half-module investigations show that multicommutation effects can be effectively emulated by increasing the commutation loop inductance through a reduced DC-link capacitor configuration. The good agreement between synchronous and emulated multicommutation confirms that inductive coupling within the commutation path is the dominant mechanism.

Two-phase switching experiments reveal that the

impact of multicommutation strongly depends on the coupling between phases. In the presented inverter layout, the phase-to-phase coupling is limited, resulting in only minor differences between single-phase and multi-phase commutation. Observations also show that the turn-off behavior with different module and capacitor combinations remains very similar, indicating that the switching behavior of each phase is largely independent of the other phase.

Overall, these results confirm that simplified emulation approaches, such as virtual inductance and reduced DC-link setups proposed in [1], [2], are suitable for reproducing the fundamental mechanisms of multicommutation. The findings also emphasize that, in inverter systems, the spatial arrangement of components and the distribution of parasitic inductances can influence the switching behavior, highlighting the importance of evaluating switching performance under representative converter-level conditions.

6 Design Implications

The findings of this work have direct implications for the design of modular SiC inverter systems. Minimizing commutation loop inductance remains a key design objective, but it must be considered in the context of the complete system rather than individual phases.

The results indicate that design strategies based solely on single-module optimization may underestimate or overestimate the electrical stress under multicommutation conditions. In particular, the spatial arrangement of power modules and DC-link capacitors, and the resulting coupling of commutation paths, significantly influence the effective commutation loop inductance.

Therefore, multicommutation scenarios should be explicitly considered during the design phase. Careful layout of modules and capacitors can mitigate the resulting voltage overshoot and oscillations, helping to maintain robust switching performance in full-module inverter systems.

7 Conclusion

This paper investigated the impact of multicommutation in modular SiC-based inverter systems using both simplified half-module and full-module experimental setups.

The results show that synchronous multicommutation leads to increased voltage overshoot, stronger

oscillations, and higher switching losses compared to single commutation. These effects are primarily caused by an increase in effective commutation loop inductance due to shared current paths during simultaneous switching events.

Half-module experiments demonstrated that multicommutation effects can be emulated by intentionally increasing the commutation loop inductance. Full-module measurements further revealed that, in the presented layout, the coupling between phases is limited, resulting in only minor differences between single-phase and multi-phase switching. These findings indicate that the developed inverter layout exhibits low susceptibility to multicommutation and maintains robust switching performance even under multicommutation conditions.

Overall, the results highlight the importance of low-inductance design and the need to evaluate multicommutation effects at the system level to ensure reliable operation of modular SiC converters. The combination of careful phase placement, capacitor integration, and minimized parasitic inductances contributes to the suitability of the proposed design for high-speed, multi-phase operation.

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